

THE ROLE OF DIGITALIZATION IN THE PROSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONSUMER MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen major changes in the consumer market associated with the extensive introduction of digitalization in the development of this area of the national economy, which undoubtedly acquires an important promising role in reforming the national economy. In order for the Republic of Uzbekistan to be more open in the world, economy, fundamental reforms are needed in all areas of the economy, including in the field of the consumer market, which is important for a radical transformation of the economy.

In order for the Republic of Uzbekistan to be more open in the global economy, the processes taking place in our country over the past decades have made it possible and the radical reforms have affected all areas of the economy and, of course, in the field of information, digital technologies and telecommunications, which undoubtedly influenced the results of the radical transformation.

The positive result from the received high-quality education, innovation and digital development of the national economy today depends on the significant growth of digitalization of the national economy in the context of globalization of the world economy and the technological development of the state. In the current period, the development of the national economy of our republic largely depends on the implementation of measures developed by the state regarding digitalization and innovation in economic development as a result of the correct and specific use of modern digital technologies for their intended purpose. And here the consumer market in Uzbekistan and its prospective development plays an important role.

Today, the share of the country's consumer market accounts for almost 90% of retail turnover, about 3/4 of which are imported goods. The share of consumed imported food products, ensuring the economic security of the country, according to international expert estimates, amounted to more than 35%, and this undoubtedly leads to the fact that satisfying the demand of consumers of the population entailed the problem of unorganized trade, which sharply affected imported products [3, p. 112].

In this regard, the role of state regulation of finished supplies has noticeably weakened and led to the fact that the problem of accounting and regulation of this process has arisen.

There is a need to use modern digital technologies as quickly and efficiently as possible, allowing for control and analysis of the consumer market.

A positive result in the development of the consumer market in the country can be ensured by innovative, technological and digital development in the context of globalization of the world economy. In the current period, the development of the national economy of our republic largely depends on the implementation of measures developed by the state regarding issues of digitalization and innovation in the consumer market.

A necessary condition for the development of market transformations in our society has become digitalization, innovative approaches and phenomena that manifest themselves in all sectors of the economy.

The consumer market has also become an innovative product of sustainable development of the state, which, based on advanced information and communication and computer technologies, can affect the entire economic market, since the supply of goods and products must be strictly controlled by the relevant authorities responsible for meeting the requirements of both the buyer and the seller in the market. This can also include services.

Digitalization in the consumer market will make it possible to use modern technologies at a high level, which is confirmed by the result of the analysis of the problems that still exist in our republic today [5, p. 3].

But on the other hand, without studying the political, economic, social and other foundations, it is impossible to achieve positive results in the development of the consumer market. New innovations and its individual areas are in line with the Program for the Development of the Digital Economy in the Consumer Market adopted by the Government.

In our country, a lot of fruitful work is being done in this direction in order to use digital technologies in this area of the economy [1, p. 2].

The opportunity to sharply increase the market of digital services aimed at servicing all, without exception, spheres of the national economy is the result of the developed Program "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and the requirements of the head of state, expressed in the address to the people of the republic and the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main task of our state at the current stage of development is, on the basis of the received high-quality education, the widespread mastery of skills in information and communication and digital technologies [2, p. 4].

Recently, everyone, without exception, uses the services of digital and information technologies for the development of both business and the consumer market of the republic. During the pandemic, which spread throughout the world, in many, led to the fact that it greatly complicated the daily life and established foundations of people, and global networks are used always and in everything at the first request of a person.

Today, many countries of the world have problems in the development, improvement of digital and information technologies, our country undoubtedly belongs to them. Telecommunication infrastructure and communications are not yet developing at a sufficiently high level required today.

Today, in the age of digitalization of all areas of our life, when hiring people, the main selection criterion is undoubtedly knowledge, skills, and abilities in working with information and communication technologies, computerization, which is a factor in the effective development of human capital and the entire economy as a whole.

In this direction, it is necessary to focus on training in modern computer technology, to provide educational institutions, which must take this into account in their educational process, with the opportunity to more widely use the opportunity to practically use the acquired digital skills.

To increase the level of competition, which is so necessary in the consumer market, large-scale work is being carried out in the country to teach skills in modern information and communication technologies, and this is currently no secret. To do this, it is necessary to purchase modern technical and technological equipment in the consumer market, and attract specialists from foreign countries [1, p. 2].

For our republic, the main, strategic task has become to increase the level of knowledge in innovative development and obtaining professional quality education, in mastering the skills of working in technologies related to digitalization. The solution of issues related to the use of innovative approaches in computer technologies directly depends on the quality of education of students and this, in our opinion, will significantly affect the improvement of skills in the consumer market [5, p. 97].

Now the main task in the implementation of the accelerated introduction of digital technologies in the consumer market is to increase and qualitatively improve mobile services of global networks in order to radically change the existing digital divide for the better.

For comparison, it can be said that this year in Uzbekistan, compared with the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, the average speed of mobile and broadband Internet is almost one and a half times lower, which negatively affects the consumer market, since the Internet has become a prerequisite for calculating all revenues to the state budget.

A special place here is given to marketing services, as one of the effective ways to regulate the consumer services market. It should be especially noted that the use of digital skills in certain segments of the consumer market should improve the contingency of this market, allowing to satisfy the growing needs of consumers for goods and services.

It should be noted here that this will help the low-income population to purchase durable products at an affordable price and not inferior in quality to other products. With the control of tax and other services with the help of technical means of computing technology, it will allow to quickly obtain a reliable picture of the state of the consumer market using digital methods of sociological survey.

The use of new changes in the consumer market of existing systems of the regulatory framework is of great importance today. With the help of modern digital technologies, it will be possible to control and effectively influence the adopted and adopted laws in business. Here, the ability to use modern technologies will be of great importance, which will ultimately make it possible to exercise control over the implementation of relevant laws and regulations, the formation of a civilized consumer market model that meets the requirements of a market economy [3, p. 11].

Innovations in the consumer market should be using digital, information technologies, which can properly influence the development of the national economy [5, p. 33]. But here some requirements may appear, in which the following can be highlighted:

- it is necessary to say that there are approaches and requirements when using digital technologies that should make it possible to promptly regulate what is happening in the consumer market;

- there should be a clear definition in the consumer market of what information is needed to effectively determine the list of goods and services that are most advantageously used in the market, and digital technologies should prove themselves in this.

- thanks to multimedia computer technology, it is necessary to organize work to improve the methods of determining the need for digital technologies in a particular issue related to the development of consumer demand in entrepreneurship.

In the context of expanding market relations and globalization of the economy, the success of the activities of market participants can be ensured with an established system of digital technologies. Therefore, the necessary financial support for the acquisition and use of modern means of processing and various types of calculation of the work of individual entrepreneurs is called upon to play an important role in the consumer market.

In order to use computer technologies in the consumer market, interacting proposals for investment and demand are needed, which could initiate the formation of a systemic, synergistic effect that contributes to an overall increase in the rate of economic growth. Thus, the application of currently existing innovative approaches in the consumer market using advanced technologies will allow future specialists to delve deeper into the process of learning and practical use of knowledge and skills in the digital space. It would be absolutely correct that in order to fully use the capabilities of modern technologies in the consumer market, it would allow for a deeper mastery of digital and information technology skills. An important role here should be played by modern technical means and technologies, to which the government of the republic pays constant attention today [5, p. 72].

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